

التحري عن جين *mecA* وجين *vanA* في العنقودية الذهبية والعنقودية الجلدية من العينات المرضية

Detection of *mecA* Gene, *vanA* Gene in *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Staphylococcus Epidermidis* from Clinical Samples

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Abstract الملخص

هدفت الدراسة الحالية إلى استعراض سلالات كل من العنقودية الذهبية والعنقودية الجلدية، واستقصاء جين المقاومة للميتيسلين *mecA* والفانكوميسين *vanA* في هذه الجراثيم، واكتشاف مقاومتها للمضادات الحيوية. جرى الحصول على العينات من ثلاث مستشفيات: الموساة، الأطفال، والأمراض الجلدية والزهرية في الفترة ما بين آب ٢٠١٣ وحتى حزيران ٢٠١٤. ولقد اكتشفت ٤٦ سلالة من العنقودية الذهبية والجلدية، حيث أظهرت نتائج PCR عصابات مفردة لكل من جين *nuc*، وجين *mecA*، وجين *vanA*، التي ترمز مناطق طولها تقريباً 270 bp، و533 bp، و1100 bp، على الترتيب. وكانت نسبة وجود جين *mecA* في سلالات العنقودية الذهبية (MRSA) ١٥%، ونسبة وجود جين *vanA* كانت ٢,٥%. وكانت نسب المقاومة للمضادات الحيوية كالآتي: الأوغمانتين AMC (٦٥%)، أمبيسلين (٧٠%)، أموكساسيلين (٥٥%)، جنتاميسين (٣٠%)، سيفترياكسون (٦٢,٥%)، بيفلوكساسين (٧,٥%)، أوفلوكساسين (٧,٥%)، فانكوميسين (٢,٥%). وكان التركيز الأصغري المثبط للميتيسلين MIC بالنسبة للعنقودية الذهبية ضمن مجال بين ١٦-٣٢ مكغ/مل، ما عدا السلالات المقاومة فكانت أكثر من ٢٥٦ مكغ/مل. بينما MIC للفانكوميسين كان ضمن مجال بين ٤-٨ مكغ/مل، ما عدا السلالات المقاومة فكانت أكثر من ٢٥٦ مكغ/مل. أما التركيز الأصغري المثبط للميتيسلين بالنسبة لكل سلالات العنقودية الجلدية فكان ضمن مجال بين 8-16 مكغ/مل.

Current study aimed to identify *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* strains, and investigate of methicillin resistant gene *mecA* and vancomycin *vanA* gene in these bacteria and detection the antimicrobial resistance. The samples were obtained from three hospitals: Al-Mouwasat, Children, and Dermal Venereal Diseases between August 2013 through June 2014. Forty six strains of *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* were detected, PCR product appeared a single DNA band for *nuc*, *mecA* and *vanA* genes, which coded areas equal to nearly 270 bp, 533 bp, and 1100 bp respectively. The percentage of presence of *mecA* gene in *S. aureus* strains (MRSA) was 15% and *vanA* gene (VRSA) was 2.5%. The percentages of antibiotic resistance were: AMC (65%), AM (70%),

AX (55%), GN (30%), CRO (62.5%), PE (7.5%), OFX (7.5%) and VA (2.5%). The MIC of *S. aureus* was ranging between 16 – 32 µg ml⁻¹, except resistant strains was >256 µg ml⁻¹ while MIC for vancomycin was ranging between 4 – 8 µg ml⁻¹, except resistant strains was >256 µg ml⁻¹. Whereas the MIC for methicillin of all strains of *S. epidermidis* was ranging between 8 – 16 µg ml⁻¹.

الكلمات المفتاح Key wards: مقاومة المضاد الحيوي Antibiotic resistance، العنقودية الذهبية MRSA، جين *mecA*، *nuc*، *vanA*، CNS.

Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is a major pathogen for humans, and it is a frequent pathogen in nosocomial infections and limited outbreaks in hospitals. Almost every person will have some type of *S. aureus* infection during a lifetime, ranging in severity from food poisoning or minor skin infections to severe life-threatening infections (1, 2). *S. aureus* is a zoonotic and human pathogen that can cause a wide range of human infections from pimples and boils to pneumonia, food poisoning, bloodstream, respiratory tract, UTIs and surgical wound infections. Furthermore, skin infections, osteomyelitis and acute endocarditis (3, 4).

Coagulase Negative Staphylococci (CNS), especially *Staphylococcus epidermidis* cause mainly foreign body infections like intravascular catheters, continuous ambulant peritoneal dialysis (CAPD) catheters, endoprostheses, metal plates and screws in osteosynthesis, cardiac pacemakers, artificial heart valves, and shunt valves, in addition, *S. epidermidis* is more often resistant to antimicrobial drugs in these cases (3, 5), where Palazzo et al. (6) published the first report of vancomycin-resistant Staphylococci isolated from healthy carriers; Wolk et al. (7) showed rapid detection and sensitivity of *S. aureus* and MRSA in wound and blood cultures; Al-

Obeid et al. (8) showed the first detection of an invasive *S. aureus* strain with reduced susceptibility to glycopeptides; Bhargava and Zhang (9) isolated and characterized 87 strains of CNS from food animals by molecular methods and studied antimicrobial susceptibility; Gutierrez et al. (10) identified the hospitalized children with Staphylococcal infections through the California office of statewide health planning and development discharge database between 1985 – 2009; De Matos et al. (11) evaluated the synergistic activity of antimicrobial drugs against lineages of forty two MRSA isolates carrying SCC*mec* IV. The aim of current study was (i) identification of *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* strains, then investigation of *mecA* and *vanA* genes in these bacteria. (ii) detection the antimicrobial resistance by disc diffusion with MICs in these bacteria.

Materials and Methods

Bacterial strains

Between 8/2013 – 6/2014 a total of 46 staphylococcal strains were isolated from clinical samples (ear, urine, eye, CSF, brain peritoneal shunt, bronchial lavages, pleural effusion, abscess, furuncle, bullous, Pus, Wound, face and hand) from Damascus city. The samples were obtained from three hospitals: Al-Mouwasat, Children, and

Dermal and Venereal Diseases.

Identification of strains

The isolates obtained from the clinical specimens were seeded onto Nutrient Agar NA (Abtec, England) and stained by the Gram stain. According to the Bergey's manual (12), the genus *Staphylococcus* was differentiated from *Streptococcus* by testing catalase test. *S. aureus* was distinguished from other species, by seeded onto mannitol salt agar MSA (Biolife, Italy), blood agar BA (Abtec, England), coagulase slide test (Sigma, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Further biochemical identification of *Staphylococci* to the species level was performed using API Staph (BioMérieux, France). The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. (12, 13).

After species confirmation, the isolates were stored on NA slants at 4°C and in nutrient broth NB (SRL, India) with 20% glycerol (v/v) at -30°C freezer. Routinely, fresh bacterial cultures were obtained from frozen stocks before each experiment and were grown at 24°C in NA (14).

Molecular methods

DNA extraction

Staphylococci were grown in 50 ml Nutrient Broth NB (SRL, India) for 24 h., then DNA extraction was done according to (15, 16) with simple modifications.

PCR conditions for Detection of *nuc*, *mecA*, and *vanA* genes

PCR was performed using *S. aureus* species-specific primers (Alpha DNA, Canada) for the *nuc* gene, which codes for thermostable nuclease using the primers, F(5'-GCGATTGATGGTGAT

ACGGTT-3') and R (5'-AGCCAAGC CTTGACGAACTAAAGC-3') as described by (17), generating ~ 270 bp. PCR amplification of *mecA* gene was performed on 0.5 µg of genomic DNA, primers for the detection of *mecA* were F (5'-AGTTGTAGTTGTCGGGTTT-3') and R(5'-AGTGGAACGAAGGTATC ATC-3') (17) generating a 533 bp. Finally the *vanA* gene was amplified with specific primers. The primers for amplification of *vanA* were F (5'- ATG AATAGAATAAAAGTTGC-3') and R (5'-TCACCCCTTTAACGCTAATA-3') as described by (18) generating a 1100 bp. The PCR was carried out in 25µl volumes under the following conditions: 100 ng genomic DNA, 12.5 µl of One PCRTM Master Mix (which contains Taq DNA polymerase, PCR buffer, dNTPs, gel loading dyes and fluorescence dye), 250 nM of each primer, and nuclease free water was added to make up the final volume of 25 µl. The reaction conditions consisted of one initial denaturation cycle at 94°C for 3 min., 45 cycles of 94°C for 1 min., 55°C (for *nuc* and *vanA*) and 58 °C (for *mecA*) for 1 min and 72°C for 2 min., and a final extension step at 72°C for 10 min. then cold 4°C. Amplifications were performed in Bioer thermal cycler (China). The amplified products were run on a 1.25% agarose gel and visualized on a u.v. transilluminator.

Antibiotic susceptibility

All tested *Staphylococci* samples were tested against susceptibility for eight antibiotics using Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion assay following the recommendations of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (19). Isolates were streaked on Mueller-

Hinton agar (Merck, Germany) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. with the following antibiotic: amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (AMC, 30µg), (gentamicin, 10 µg), (ceftriaxone, 30 µg), (pefloxacin, 5 µg), (ofloxacin, 5 µg) and (ampicillin, 10 µg), (vancomycin, 30 µg.) (amoxicillin, 25µg). All discs were obtained from (Bio-analyze, Turkey). Inhibition zone diameters were measured and studied using norms of the National Committee on Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS) (Table, 1).

MIC determination

Determination of MIC of methicillin and vancomycin (Sigma- Aldrich) were determined by broth dilution method using CLSI guidelines (19). The Antibiotics were dissolved in distilled water with 1 ml inoculum (0.5 McFarland) of Staphylococci and serial dilutions were made in NB ranging from 256 - 4 µg ml. All the tubes were incubated for 24 hrs. at 37°C. MICs were determined as the lowest

concentration of antibiotics that showed no visible growth of the Staphylococci.

Results and Discussion

Bacterial Identification

All the strains S1 to S46 were found to be gram positive cocci in clusters and catalase test. All the strains of *S. aureus* were isolated from patients were Positive response for (mannitol fermentation, coagulase slide test). After confirmation the characteristics upon biochemical tests and API Staph. the results were submitted to 40 *S. aureus*. and 6 *S. epidermidis*.

Antibiotic susceptibility tests

Strains of *S. aureus* showed different level of resistance against some antibiotics. Inhibition zone diameters were measured depending on NCCLS. The results of antibiotic resistance tests of *S. aureus* was as follows: amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (65%), gentamicin (30%), ceftriaxone (62.5%), pefloxacin (7.5%), ofloxacin (7.5%) ampicillin (70%), vancomycin (2.5%) and amoxicillin (55%) (Table 1, Fig. 1, 2).

Table 1: the percentage of antimicrobial resistance for *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*.

Antibiotics	<i>S. aureus</i> (40)		<i>S. epidermidis</i> (6)	
	R %	S%	R%	S%
Ampicillin AM 10	70	30	100	-
Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid AMC 30	65	35	16.66	83.33
Amoxicillin AX 25	55	45	33.33	66.66
Gentamicin GM 10	30	70	16.66	83.33
Ceftriaxone CRO 30	62.5	37.5	33.33	66.66
Vancomycin VA 30	2.5	97.5	-	100
Ofloxacin OFX 5	7.5	92.5	-	100
Pefloxacin PE 5	7.5	92.5	-	100

R: resistant, S: sensitive

Figure 1: The percentage of antibiotic resistance for *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, AMC amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (30µg), AM ampicillin (10 µg), AX amoxicillin (25), vancomycin (30 µg), Gent. gentamicin (10 µg), OFX ofloxacin (5 µg), PE pefloxacin (5 µg) and CRO ceftriaxone (30 µg).

Figure 2: Disc diffusion method with inhibition zones(mm) for some antibiotics against *S. aureus*, AM(0), AX(13), AMC(16) VA(20).

The MIC for methicillin of all strains of *S. aureus* was ranging between 16 – 32 µg ml⁻¹ except the strains which carry *mecA* gene (S3, S11, S19, S28, S31, S32) was >256 µg ml⁻¹, but MIC for vancomycin was ranging between 4 – 8 µg ml⁻¹ except the strain which carry *vanA* gene (S15) was >256 µg ml⁻¹. Whereas The MIC for methicillin of all strains of *S. epidermidis* was ranging

between 8 – 16 µg ml⁻¹. These results like some studies as a (6) which carried out in Brazil, where MIC was 4 µg ml for *S. epidermidis*, and study of (15), while different of study (17) where showed that some strains of *S. aureus* had a MIC >256 µg ml⁻¹ and others had <8 µg ml⁻¹ and against vancomycin was found that 53% of isolates had 4 µg ml⁻¹.

Detection of *nuc*, *mecA*, and *vanA* genes

Genotyping have been used for the detection of clinical isolates to guide the management of nosocomial infections. However, a variety of markers can be used for typing and results accordingly reflect the choice of markers. In Current study it has been identified the *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, then detected the *mecA* gene and *vanA* gene, moreover, the antimicrobial resistance by disc diffusion with MICs in these bacteria. For molecular characterization the amplifying thermostable nuclease (*nuc*) gene encoded to enzyme thermonuclease and the PCR product appeared a single DNA band with a size equal to ~ 270 bp corresponding to the *nuc* gene. The *mecA* gene was detected in all strains by the PCR amplification method. PCR amplification of *mecA* gene was positive in 6 of 40 strains (MRSA): S3, S11, S19, S28, S31, S32, but the others 34 strains were MSSA Methicillin-sensitive *Staph. aureus*, where the percentage of presence of *mecA* was (15%) (Table 2, Fig. 3). While for *S. epidermidis* *mecA* gene was not founded in any strain. The strains which were carried out *mecA* gene showed resistance to amoxicillin, ampicillin, amoxicillin clavulanic acid. By *S. aureus* and based on antibiotic resistance discs there are 28 strains resistant to ampicillin and 22 strains resistant to amoxicillin, but only 6 strains were carried out *mecA* gene, that is to say not all strains of *S. aureus* can be classified MRSA, like S1, S2, S6, S15 which were resistant to (AMC,

AM, AX) but it didn't carry *mecA* gene. The repression of *mecA* gene and the resulting absence of MR in some of the isolates could be due to several factors. Both genetic and environmental factors play a significant role in the expression of MR. While all strains of *S. epidermidis* were sensitive for all tested antibiotics and this agree with genetic results, where *mecA* gene didn't found in any strains.

In contrast to previously reported MRSA isolates, Khan et al. (20) showed that 7 isolates of 17 were carried out by *mecA* gene; Buzaid et al. (21) reported that 31 % of *S. aureus* were MRSA in tertiary surgical and trauma hospital; Abd-El Hafez et al. (22) showed that 29 isolates of *S. epidermidis* were positive for the *mecA* gene, and these isolates showed several multidrug-resistance patterns; Bhargava and Zhang (9) detected the *mecA* gene in 60 of 87 CNS isolates and studied their antimicrobial susceptibility to some antibiotics; Lye et al. (23) appeared that about 73 of 100 *S. aureus* were isolated from workers were positive for *mecA* gene; Sergelidis et al. (24) isolated methicillin-resistant *staphylococcus spp.* from ready to eat fish products and showed presence the *mecA* gene in two oxacillin-resistant strains and three (23.1%) of *S. epidermidis*.

PCR results of *mecA* gene gave sharp differentiation between many strains which help in determination of the suspected source of infection especially in nosocomial infection cases also in case of repeated infections with the same strain in case of treatment failure or insufficient disinfection.

The sequenced *vanA* gene PCR product (Table 2, Fig. 4) was positive only in one strain of *S. aureus* S15 (VRSA) with percentage (2.5%) and gave a 1100 bp but none of the others. While for *S. epidermidis* it didn't found *vanA* gene in any strain. In conclusion vancomycin resistance the almost strains of *S. aureus* were sensitive to vancomycin, so these results agree with genetic data where no strains of *S. aureus* carried *vanA* gene except S15. These results like the results in some researches and unlike the others, where Kondoh et al. (25) showed that of 78 MRSA strains was one strain VRSA and five showed a hetero-VRSA pattern with 4–8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for MIC; Adam et al. (26) detected and characterized the

heterogeneous Vancomycin-Intermediate *S. aureus* were isolated in Canada and showed the differences between the value of MIC in these strains; Azimian et al. (27) isolated resistant strains of *S. aureus* from the respiratory tract of a patient in university hospital carried *vanA* with 713 bp and isolated some strains of CNS didn't carry *vanA* gene; Entenza et al. (28) investigated the potential of microcalorimetry to detect reduced susceptibility to vancomycin in MRSA strains comparing with VSSA, VISA, VRSA as a reference clinical strains. In conclusion, just the clinical *S. aureus* strains which have high value of MIC of methicillin or vancomycin, have *mecA* or *vanA* genes.

Figure 3: 1.25% Agarose gel electrophoresis for the detection of *mecA* gene (533 bp) in *S. aureus* by PCR, Lane 4: *S. aureus* 28 from bronchial lavages , Lane 6: *S. aureus* 31 from ear, Lane 7: *S. aureus* S 32 from Conjunctivitis, M: 50 bp DNA Ladder.

Figure 4: 1.25% Agarose gel electrophoresis for the detection of *vanA* gene (1100 bp) in *S. aureus* by PCR, Lane 3: *S. aureus* S 15 from urine and others strains are negative M: 50 bp DNA Ladder .

Table 2: *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* which positive or negative to *mecA* and *vanA* genes

No.	Staphylococci strains	source's samples	<i>mecA</i>	<i>vanA</i>	MIC _{met} $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	MIC _{van} $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
S1	<i>S. aureus</i>	abscess	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S2	<i>S. aureus</i>	bronchial lavages	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S3	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	+	-	>256	4 – 8
S4	<i>S. aureus</i>	CSF	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S5	<i>S. aureus</i>	ear	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S6	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S7	<i>S. aureus</i>	Pus	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S8	<i>S. aureus</i>	CSF	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S9	<i>S. aureus</i>	ear	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S10	<i>S. aureus</i>	bronchial lavages	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S11	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	+	-	>256	4 – 8
S12	<i>S. aureus</i>	bullous	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S13	<i>S. aureus</i>	eye	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S14	<i>S. aureus</i>	urine	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S15	<i>S. aureus</i>	urine	-	+	16-32	>256
S16	<i>S. aureus</i>	urine	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S17	<i>S. aureus</i>	abscess	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S18	<i>S. aureus</i>	eye	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S19	<i>S. aureus</i>	ear	+	-	>256	4 – 8

S20	<i>S. aureus</i>	hand	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S21	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S22	<i>S. aureus</i>	Furuncle	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S23	<i>S. aureus</i>	Peritoneal fluid	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S24	<i>S. aureus</i>	Brain Peritoneal shunt	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S25	<i>S. aureus</i>	urine	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S26	<i>S. aureus</i>	Pleural effusion	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S27	<i>S. aureus</i>	wound	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S28	<i>S. aureus</i>	bronchial lavages	+	-	>256	4 – 8
S29	<i>S. aureus</i>	CSF	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S30	<i>S. aureus</i>	CSF	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S31	<i>S. aureus</i>	ear	+	-	>256	4 – 8
S32	<i>S. aureus</i>	Conjunctivitis	+	-	>256	4 – 8
S33	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S34	<i>S. aureus</i>	face	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S35	<i>S. aureus</i>	abscess	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S36	<i>S. aureus</i>	pus	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S37	<i>S. aureus</i>	bullous	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S38	<i>S. aureus</i>	abscess	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S39	<i>S. aureus</i>	CSF	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S40	<i>S. aureus</i>	face	-	-	16-32	4 – 8
S41	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	Peritoneal fluid	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8
S42	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	CSF	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8
S43	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	ear	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8
S44	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	CSF	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8
S45	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	face	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8
S46	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	mouth	-	-	8 – 16	4 – 8

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